

Scientific article

Profit-optimal data-driven operation of a hybrid power plant participating in energy markets

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Abstract: *An energy management system (EMS) is formulated for a hybrid power plant (HPP), consisting of a wind power plant and battery storage plant, participating in bidding stages in the German energy market. The EMS utilizes supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) measurements from the site to improve power forecast from the wind power plant. First, the measurement data is used together with numerical weather prediction data to accurately forecast local wind conditions. Second, the measurement data is used to adapt a baseline engineering wake model that gives the total wind power generation for a given input wind condition. The EMS also uses an online cyclic damage minimization approach to accurately balance the battery damage cost against the revenue obtained by market bidding. An HPP controller is formulated to ensure proper tracking of optimal set-points. When compared with the industry standard, the proposed formulation shows an accurate estimation and balancing of revenue and costs and a significant reduction in the power deviation penalty, which leads to significantly higher overall profit.*

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